

Example of a Complex Number Identity Method Proof

This appendix provides a complete and explicit walkthrough of a CNI proof of Thales' theorem (cf. Figure A.1 for an illustration). We follow the presentation by [2] and expand the intermediate steps in a structured form to illustrate how the theorem is translated into complex number representations.

Theorem A.1 (Thales' Theorem). Let A, B be distinct points. Let O be the midpoint of \overline{AB} and let C be a point on the circle with diameter AB (equivalently $OA = OB = OC$). Then

$$AC \perp BC. \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Figure A.1: Illustration of Thales' Theorem.

The CNI method translates the hypotheses and the thesis into realness constraints of rational expressions in complex point coordinates. One then proves the theorem by constructing a short identity that forces the thesis expression to be real.

All expressions below involve divisions – hence, we assume that the corresponding denominators are nonzero. In particular, $A \neq B$ and $O \neq A, B$, and we exclude trivial cases where $C = A$ or $C = B$. The automated procedure handles such issues via a separate elimination check [2].

Step 1: Complex representation.

We model the plane as \mathbb{C} and represent points by their complex coordinates (affixes), using the same symbols:

$$A, B, C, O \in \mathbb{C}.$$

Directed segments are differences of affixes, for example, \overrightarrow{AB} corresponds to $B - A$.

Step 2: Translate the hypotheses into realness constraints.

Kovács and Peng encode the construction with three realness constraints [2]. For clarity, we introduce names for the left-hand sides and explicitly define the real variables r_1, r_2, r_3 .

Since A, O, B are collinear, the directed vectors $\overrightarrow{OA} = A - O$ and $\overrightarrow{OB} = B - O$ are parallel (i.e., they point along the same line, possibly with opposite orientation). Therefore, there exists a real scalar $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$A - O = \lambda(O - B).$$

Assuming $O \neq B$, dividing by $(O - B)$ yields

$$\frac{A - O}{O - B} = \lambda \in \mathbb{R},$$

which motivates the CNI realness constraint

$$r_1 := \frac{A - O}{O - B} \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

The condition $OA = OC$ implies that $\triangle OAC$ is isosceles with equal legs OA and OC (cf. Figure A.2). Hence, the base angles at A and C are equal,

$$\angle OAC \equiv \angle ACO \pmod{\pi}. \quad (\text{A.3})$$

In the complex plane, directed angles can be represented using arguments of quotients of complex differences [1, 3]. More precisely, for nonzero vectors $u, v \in \mathbb{C}$, the directed angle from v to u satisfies

$$\angle(v, u) \equiv \arg\left(\frac{u}{v}\right) \pmod{2\pi}. \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Applying (A.4) to (A.3) yields

$$\arg\left(\frac{C - A}{O - A}\right) \equiv \arg\left(\frac{O - C}{A - C}\right) \pmod{\pi},$$

because $\angle OAC$ is the angle from \overrightarrow{AO} to \overrightarrow{AC} and $\angle ACO$ is the angle from \overrightarrow{CA} to \overrightarrow{CO} . Subtracting the two arguments gives

$$\arg\left(\frac{\frac{C-A}{O-A}}{\frac{O-C}{A-C}}\right) \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi}.$$

A complex number has argument 0 modulo π if and only if it is real. Therefore,

$$\frac{\frac{C-A}{O-A}}{\frac{O-C}{A-C}} \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Up to consistent sign conventions (replacing $C - A$ with $-(A - C)$ and $O - A$ with $-(A - O)$), this is exactly the CNI realness constraint used by Kovács and Peng [2]:

$$r_2 := \frac{\frac{A-C}{A-O}}{\frac{C-O}{C-A}} \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Figure A.2: The auxiliary segment CO highlights the isosceles triangle OAC (since $OA = OC$), hence $\angle OAC = \angle ACO$.

For later simplification, it is useful to rewrite r_2 algebraically:

$$r_2 = \frac{A - C}{A - O} \cdot \frac{C - A}{C - O} = -\frac{(A - C)^2}{(A - O)(C - O)}. \quad (\text{A.6})$$

(The sign appears because $C - A = -(A - C)$.)

Similarly, $OB = OC$ makes $\triangle OBC$ isosceles and yields the realness constraint

$$r_3 := \frac{\frac{B-O}{B-C}}{\frac{C-B}{C-O}} \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (\text{A.7})$$

Again, we rewrite r_3 in a form convenient for cancellation:

$$r_3 = \frac{B - O}{B - C} \cdot \frac{C - O}{C - B} = -\frac{(B - O)(C - O)}{(B - C)^2}. \quad (\text{A.8})$$

(Here we use $(B - C)(C - B) = -(B - C)^2$.)

Step 3: Translate the thesis into a realness constraint.

The goal $AC \perp BC$ is encoded in the CNI approach by the expression

$$r := \left(\frac{C - B}{C - A} \right)^2 \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (\text{A.9})$$

We now explain why (A.9) captures perpendicularity (in the intended context).

Let $u := C - B$ and $v := C - A$ denote the complex representatives of the directed vectors \overrightarrow{BC} and \overrightarrow{AC} , respectively. Assume $u \neq 0$ and $v \neq 0$. Write u and v in polar form,

$$u = |u|e^{i\theta_u}, \quad v = |v|e^{i\theta_v}.$$

Then

$$\frac{u}{v} = \frac{|u|}{|v|} e^{i(\theta_u - \theta_v)}. \quad (\text{A.10})$$

The angle between the directions of u and v is $\varphi \equiv \theta_u - \theta_v \pmod{2\pi}$. Therefore, (A.10) shows that the argument of $\frac{u}{v}$ encodes the directed angle between the two lines.

If $AC \perp BC$, then the direction of u is obtained from the direction of v by a rotation of $\pm\frac{\pi}{2}$, i.e., $\varphi \equiv \pm\frac{\pi}{2} \pmod{\pi}$. Equivalently, the quotient $\frac{u}{v}$ is purely imaginary:

$$\frac{u}{v} = \lambda i \quad \text{for some } \lambda \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Squaring removes the factor i and produces a real (negative) number:

$$\left(\frac{u}{v}\right)^2 = (\lambda i)^2 = -\lambda^2 \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Substituting back $u = C - B$ and $v = C - A$ gives exactly (A.9). This explains why (A.9) is a convenient algebraic predicate for perpendicularity in the CNI setting [2, 4].

However, the converse implication is not unique to the perpendicular case. If $AC \parallel BC$, then $\frac{u}{v} = \lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ for some λ , and therefore $\left(\frac{u}{v}\right)^2 = \lambda^2 \in \mathbb{R}$ as well. Hence, the condition (A.9) holds for both $\varphi \equiv 0 \pmod{\pi}$ (parallel) and $\varphi \equiv \pm\frac{\pi}{2} \pmod{\pi}$ (perpendicular). Therefore, Kovács and Peng interpret (A.9) together with non-degeneracy assumptions and the construction context to exclude the unintended parallel case [2].

Step 4: Manual CNI proof through a single identity.

The characteristic CNI step is to show that multiplying the hypothesis expressions by the thesis expression yields a real constant [2].

We compute the product using the simplified forms (A.6) and (A.8):

$$r_1 r_2 r_3 r = \frac{A - O}{O - B} \cdot \left(-\frac{(A - C)^2}{(A - O)(C - O)}\right) \cdot \left(-\frac{(B - O)(C - O)}{(B - C)^2}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{(C - B)^2}{(C - A)^2}\right). \quad (\text{A.11})$$

Now, cancel factors step by step:

- $(A - O)$ cancels between the first and second factors.
- $(C - O)$ cancels between the second and third factors.
- $(B - C)^2 = (C - B)^2$ (because squaring removes the sign), hence the third and fourth factors cancel.
- $(A - C)^2 = (C - A)^2$, and hence the second and fourth factors cancel.
- The two minus signs from r_2 and r_3 cancel.
- Finally, $(B - O) = -(O - B)$, so $\frac{B - O}{O - B} = -1$.

Therefore,

$$r_1 r_2 r_3 r = -1. \quad (\text{A.12})$$

Under the hypotheses, we have $r_1, r_2, r_3 \in \mathbb{R}$. From (A.12) we obtain

$$r = -\frac{1}{r_1 r_2 r_3}. \quad (\text{A.13})$$

If $r_1 r_2 r_3 \neq 0$, then the right-hand side is real (closure of \mathbb{R} under multiplication and division by nonzero values), hence $r \in \mathbb{R}$ and the thesis (A.9) holds.

Step 5: Mechanized proof through elimination ideals.

The automated version replaces the informal ‘‘simplify the product’’ step with an elimination computation. Kovács and Peng introduce real variables r_1, r_2, r_3 for the hypotheses and r for the thesis and compute an elimination ideal in $\mathbb{Q}[r, r_1, r_2, r_3]$ [2].

Start from the four equations

$$\frac{A - O}{O - B} - r_1 = 0, \quad (\text{A.14})$$

$$\frac{A - C}{A - O} \Big/ \frac{C - O}{C - A} - r_2 = 0, \quad (\text{A.15})$$

$$\frac{B - O}{B - C} \Big/ \frac{C - B}{C - O} - r_3 = 0, \quad (\text{A.16})$$

$$\left(\frac{C - B}{C - A}\right)^2 - r = 0. \quad (\text{A.17})$$

These are rational equations because of the divisions. Since elimination is performed in a polynomial ring, the next step is to clear the denominators [2].

Clearing denominators transforms (A.14)–(A.17) into polynomial equations $p_1 = \dots = p_s = 0$. However, clearing the denominators alone would allow for solutions where the denominator is zero. To exclude this, [1] introduce a slack variable u and add an additional polynomial

$$p_{s+1} = (b_1 b_2 \dots b_m) u - 1, \quad (\text{A.18})$$

where b_1, \dots, b_m are all denominators that occur in the input expressions. This enforces $b_1 \dots b_m \neq 0$ and is called *Rabinowitsch trick* [2].

Let $J = \langle p_1, \dots, p_s, p_{s+1} \rangle$ be the ideal in the full polynomial ring. Elimination removes the point variables (and u) and produces

$$I = J \cap \mathbb{Q}[r, r_1, r_2, r_3].$$

Kovács and Peng [2] compute I and observe that it contains the linear polynomial

$$r_1 r_2 r_3 r + 1 \in I. \quad (\text{A.19})$$

Hence, r can be expressed as $r = -1/(r_1 r_2 r_3)$, reproducing (A.13).

The expression (A.13) requires $r_1 r_2 r_3 \neq 0$. Kovács and Peng [2] verify this by repeating elimination after additionally inserting the polynomial $r_1 r_2 r_3$ into the input: the resulting elimination ideal is $\langle 1 \rangle$, which means that the assumption $r_1 r_2 r_3 = 0$ is inconsistent with the construction constraints (no admissible solutions). Therefore, division by zero cannot occur, and the proof is mechanically sound.

Bibliography

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